

**THE EFFECT OF THE ADOPTION OF INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL
REPORTING STANDARDS (IFRSs) ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF
QUOTED OIL AND GAS COMPANIES IN NIGERIA**

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**A RESEARCH PROJECT SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF
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DECLARATION

I, Ologunja, Bolade Emmanuel declare that this research project was carried out entirely by me under the supervision of Dr. Imoleayo Obigbemi, Department of Accounting, Faculty of Management Sciences, University of Lagos. This research project has not been presented, either wholly or partly, for any degree elsewhere. I am fully responsible for all the errors that may be found in this research work.

All sources of scholarly information used in this research project are fully acknowledged by the researcher.

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this research project report titled: ‘The effect of the adoption of international financial reporting standards(IFRSs) on financial performance of quoted oil and gas companies in nigeria’ was written by Ologunja, Bolade Emmanuel with matriculation number 190201027 under my supervision.

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Date

DEDICATION

I dedicate this research project to God Almighty, the one who made my efforts a success.

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Foremost, my appreciation goes to God Almighty for His constant mercy and grace upon my life from my first day on this earth and most especially throughout my undergraduate programme at the University of Lagos.

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the effect of the adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) adoption on the financial performance of quoted oil and gas companies in Nigeria. The study evaluates the effect of IFRS adoption on earnings per share (EPS), book value per share (BVPS) and cash flow per share (CFPS) using an ex-post facto research design, the study analyzed secondary data from audited annual reports of 7 oil and gas companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NGX). The results show a significant increase in EPS ($t = 3.05$, $p = 0.005$) and profit after tax ($t = 1.21$, $p = 0.0238$) post-IFRS adoption. The mean difference in EPS is 166, with a 95% confidence interval of 54.5 to 277. However, no significant difference was found in BVPS ($t = 1.43$, $p = 0.163$). The results for CFPS were mixed, with the t-test indicating a significant difference ($t = 1.79$, $p = 0.003$), but the Wilcoxon test not supporting this finding ($p = 0.253$). The study's findings have implications for policymakers, regulators and investors. The study contributes to the existing literature on the impact of IFRS adoption on financial performance. The findings suggest that IFRS adoption leads to increased profitability and EPS. The study highlights the need for further research on the impact of IFRS adoption on other financial performance metrics.

Keywords: *International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), Earnings Per Share (EPS), Book Value Per Share (BVPS), Cash Flow Per Share (CFPS)*

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

The Financial Accounting Standards Board (FASB) and the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) have consistently given importance to furnishing high-quality financial information. Omotoso, Schutte and Oberholzer (2022) stated that International financial reporting standards constitute a code of generally accepted accounting principles (GAAP) used by companies to build financial statements, an important source of information released every year and useful to different stakeholders (shareholders, debtors, customers, workers and governments) for their understanding of the financial advancement and management stewardship of a company's assets. Meanwhile, IFRS were implemented to provide one language of accounting and thus business and accounts to be comprehensible from company to company and country to country and they specifically lay down how accountants are supposed to maintain and report their accounts (OgieAkpakpa, 2021). Ajibade (2020) opened up that it was in the year 1973 when International Accounting Standard Committee (IASC), the world's professional accounting organisations of dominant nations with 16 countries mutually agreed to outline a uniform framework of principles of accounting that are applicable internationally to take over the place of the International Accounting Standards which allowed inconsistent treatment of transactions and events frustrating comparative study. Also, because of globalization and to solve comparability issues, IASC was revamped leading to the formation of International Accounting Standard Board that issues IFRS (Okoughenu, 2020)

Nigeria implemented International financial reporting standards as one of its responses to international best practice and to adapt to the international trend of financial reporting standardization (Nwinkonzor, 2024). Nigerian Statement of Accounting Standards (SAS) convergence with IFRSs was endorsed by the Nigerian Federal Executive Council from January 1, 2012 (Titus, 2021). The Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) listed companies were compelled to accept IFRSs as of January 2012 (Nwinkonzor, 2024). The adoption was structured such that the use of IFRSs by all the stakeholders was to be in full effect come January 2014 (Madawaki, 2021). Before the adoption of IFRSs, each country used to have its local reporting standards, and in Nigeria, Nigerian Accounting Standard Board (NASB) developed the local standards known as SAS (Sanyaolu,2017). After the use of IFRSs was adopted in Nigeria, NASB was re-christened Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) (Desalegn, 2020). On the other hand, before the harmonization of IFRSs, every country makes and use their own national accounting standard while other countries are disposed towards using another country's accounting standard (Adedoyin, Ezekiel & Abiola, 2020). Hence, IFRSs variables utilized in this study are the Book Value per share (BVPS), Cashflow per share (CFPS) and Earnings per share (EPS). CFPS is a fundamental financial metric that provides an impression of a company's ability to produce cash from its operations on a per share basis (Lawrence & Joy, 2023). BVPS indicates equity for common stockholders as a percentage of outstanding shares (Ndubuisi & Regina, 2019), while total common equity indicates a company's difference between total assets and total liabilities and represents net worth due to common stockholders (Brigham & Houston, 2021).

A firm's financial performance is a firm's capacity to generate fresh resources in day-to-day operations within a given time (Bora, 2018). Financial performance involves maximizing shareholders' wealth and generating profit which are among the most important objectives of a

firm (Pandey, 2022). Firms' sales revenue growth, the rise in their profit margin, capital investment decisions and the selection of capital structure mostly influence the shareholder's wealth (Arnott & Asness, 2023). The various company's financial performance measures can be observed in the company's Return on Investment (ROI), Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), value added, among others that measure whether the owners, objectives are met; the shareholders' wealth maximization goals through investment in business (Wamugo, 2015). Return on Equity (ROE) is a crucial financial metric that approximates the profitability of an organization from the perspective of shareholders, given as a percentage of net income in comparison to the whole shareholders' equity (Bamidele, 2024).

Furthermore, the oil and gas industry are an exotic business with a lot of intricateness when it comes to the recognition, measurement, classification and accounting on the balance sheet for assets (Adamu, 2018). A separate standard IFRS 6 exploration for and valuations of mineral resources issued by the IASB is exclusive for the extractive sector to provide guidelines for accounting for acquisition, exploration and evaluation costs (Adamu & Saleh, 2018). In Nigeria however, SAS 14, Accounting in the Petroleum industry Upstream Activities and SAS 17, Accounting in the Petroleum Industry Downstream Activities are the two standards providing regulation for accounting treatment of all Oil and Gas exploration and production costs prior to IFRS implementation (Adamu & Saleh, 2018). Furthermore, oil and gas companies play a strategic role in Nigeria, playing an important role in the Nation's GDP, job creation as well as the general development of the agricultural industry (Desalegn, 2020). This study is poised to extend literature by examining the effects on key financial metrics like CFPS, BVPS and EPS. More so, stakeholders can gauge the level of transparency, comparability, and reliability in financial reporting within the sector. Ultimately, the findings of this study will provide valuable

insights for policymakers, regulators, investors, and managers, enabling them to make informed decisions and enhance the overall integrity of financial reporting in the Nigerian agricultural industry.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

The shift towards International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs) is a major development in the accounting arena, as most countries have abandoned or are abandoning their local Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP) for IFRSs. In Nigeria, the oil and gas sector, a major source of the nation's revenue and foreign exchange earnings, has been bedevilled by persistent problems of low financial reporting quality, transparency, and accountability. These issues have raised doubts about the reliability and credibility of financial statements in the industry. The implementation of IFRSs is anticipated to enhance the quality of financial reporting, attract foreign investments, and enable comparability in the international market. Notwithstanding, there is a pressing necessity to investigate the actual impact of IFRSs adoption on the financial performance of Nigerian publicly traded oil and gas companies in the face of the dynamic environment marked by volatile commodity prices, regulatory challenges, and unique operational risks.

Despite the planned benefits, IFRS adoption creates concerns in determining its effect on some of the key financial performance indicators such as Earnings Per Share (EPS), Book Value Per Share (BVS), and Cash Flow Per Share (CFPS). Such financial indicators are essential to determine profitability, asset values, and liquidity in the sector. The implementation of IFRSs involves substantial adjustments to accounting practices, which might not always yield immediate or beneficial financial outcomes. This raises crucial concerns over whether IFRSs have been successful in realizing their goal of enhancing financial performance within the

industry. Stakeholders, including investors, regulators, and management, require clarification on whether the advantages of IFRSs adoption outweigh the complexity and expense of compliance, such as system adjustment, employees' training, and procedural changes. The aim of this research is to analyse the extent to which the implementation of IFRSs has improved the financial performance of quoted oil and gas firms in Nigeria and to investigate the factors influencing the IFRSs adoption and financial performance relationship. Based on financial statements before and after IFRSs adoption, this research intends to provide useful observations and contribute to the broader discussion regarding the benefits and challenges of IFRSs adoption in emerging economies.

1.3. Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to assess the influence of adoption of IFRSs on the financial Performance of quoted oil and gas companies in Nigeria. The study's specific objectives are to:

- i. evaluates the effect of IFRS adoption on the Earnings per Share (EPS) of oil and gas firm
- ii. evaluates the effect of IFRS adoption on the Book Value per Share of oil and gas firm
- iii. evaluates the effect of IFRS adoption on the Cash flow per share of oil and gas firm.

1.4. Research Questions

This research is conducted in such a way that it provides answers to the following questions:

- i. To what extent does IFRS adoption affect Earnings Per Share of oil and gas firms?
- ii. How does IFRS adoption influence Book value per share of oil and gas firms?
- iii. What impact does IFRS adoption have on Cash flow per share of oil and gas firms?

1.5. Research Hypotheses

In view of the above objectives, the following hypotheses stated in their null forms, were formulated:

H0₁: There is no significant difference between IFRS adoption and EPS of oil and gas firms

H0₂: There is no significant difference between IFRS adoption and BVPS of oil and gas firms

H0₃: There is no significant difference between IFRS adoption and CFPS of oil and gas firms

1.6. Significance of the Study

The study would be significant to various stakeholders such as policymakers, researchers, investors and financial analysts.

The study would assist investors in making informed investment decision as whether to continue to hold their shares or to sell them off, while potential investors would be encouraged to buy new shares. It will also serve as a guide to financial analyst and managers in evaluating value of the firm. Also, to researchers the study would be of significance to both existing and future researchers for better understanding purpose and /or for reference purpose.

This study might offer a meaningful contribution to the existing body of knowledge, serving as a valuable resource for researchers and analysts. Meanwhile, policymakers can however assess and have a better understanding on the effect of IFRSs compulsory adoption on Quoted Oil and companies. Thus, this study may inspire policies or changes in regards to transparency, accuracy and comparability of the financial reporting process.

1.7. Scope and Limitation of the Study

The study focused on quoted oil and gas companies listed on NGX. The geographical scope is limited to the Nigerian business environment. The study covered Pre IFRSs (2007-2011) and

post-IFRSs (2019-2024). Historical financial data extracted from the audited annual report were analyzed. The study assessed seven (7) quoted Oil and gas companies, the sample size remains relatively robust which allows for meaningful comparisons and statistical analysis to be conducted on the available data.

Also, this study did not acknowledge other measures of accounting quality i.e. (discretionary accrual, earnings management, accounting policies etc.) which IFRSs was made to address. Nevertheless, this study adopted value relevance due to its widespread recognition in academic literature. Lastly, the study focused on quoted Oil and gas companies. thus, other oil and gas companies not quoted were not considered. The justification for this is, all oil and gas companies listed on the NGX was considered.

1.8. Operational Definition of Terms

Book Value Per Share: A financial metric that represents the total equity of a company divided by the number of outstanding shares.

Cash Flow Per Share: A financial metric that measures the amount of cash generated by a company per outstanding share of its common stock over a specific period of time.

Earnings Per Share: A financial metrics that represent the profit a company has generated per share of its outstanding ordinary shares.

Financial Reporting Quality: The degree to which financial reports accurately represent a company's financial performance and position.

International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRSs): A set of accounting standards developed by the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) to provide a common global language for financial reporting.

Loan-to-Value Ratios (LTV): Calculated as the ratio of the loan amount to the appraised value of the asset securing the loan, expressed as a percentage.

Return on Equity (ROE): Measured as net income divided by shareholders' equity, expressed as a percentage, to assess profitability.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

Preamble

This chapter is focused on expanding the horizon of the study by consulting extant literatures of scholars from Nigeria and other parts of the world. By examining various concepts and issues surrounding the subject matter from different perspectives, this chapter provides a comprehensive understanding of the research topic

2.1. Conceptual Review

2.1.1 International Financial Reporting Standards adoption in Nigeria

International Financial Reporting Standards have become a very common phenomenon owing to inevitable globalization (Al Mamun, Özcan & Uyar, 2018). International Financial Reporting Standards is globally accepted accounting standards aimed at enhancing comparability of financial reporting across countries (Fasina & Adejare, 2021). The development of international accounting standards started in 1973 when 16 Australian, Canadian, French, German, Japanese, and United States professional accounting organizations came together for this purpose. The United States, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom were among the leaders that set up the International Accounting Standards Committee, IASC, which was later reconstituted and

renamed the International Accounting Standards Board, IASB (Enahoro, 2019). This blend is highly linked with promoting economic growth and has created a heightened demand for transparent, similar, and reliable financial information in global markets (Gu & Semba, 2018). As part of this global trend, Nigeria also sought a legal framework to increase investor confidence through more stringent government control over accounting procedures and regulation of financial reporting (Ofoegbu & Odoemelam, 2018).

Internationalization of business and trade made harmonization of preparation and presentation of financial statements necessary (Edogbanya & Kamardin, 2014). Nigeria's federal government adopted 2012 as the year of compulsory adoption of IFRS in September 2010 (Masud, 2013). Nigeria's Federal Executive Council's FEC suggested in January 2012 the convergence of its domestic accounting standards, SAS with IFRS (Masud, 2013). An IFRS adoption committee was formed; the committee made implementation of IFRS effective for listed entities and public interest entities by January 2012 (Masud, 2013). The rest of the public interest entities needed to comply with the requirements by January 2013, whereas small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) were given a relief to January 2014 (Olojede & Ogundele, 2017). Although this would be, the 31 December 2010 closing balances of Nigerian listed companies as presented under IFRS were to act as starting opening balances in initial financial reports on January 1, 2012, these were to act as the basis for the first complete IFRS compliant statements as of December 31, 2012 (Ogundele, 2017). Harmonization was aimed at making Nigerian companies and other companies in Nigeria and across the world comparable (NASB, 2020). The key purpose of the establishment of IFRS is to have one set of high-quality, understandable, enforceable, and widely accepted international financial reporting standards based on clearly defined principles (Olojede, 2017).

In addition, Pologeorgis (2018) stated that the application of IFRS impacts business management, investors, stock markets, accountants, and regulatory bodies. For companies, the use of standardized accounting practices facilitates cross-border business, reduces risks, and lowers the cost of operations; this helps in raising capital at a lower cost of interest (Barth, 2020). Standardization of financial disclosure to investors removes the need for local translations, increases transparency, and provides more accurate information on which informed decisions can be made (Menicucci & Paolucci, 2016). Chouaibi and Mutar (2024) emphasize that IFRS has a huge influence on the financial reporting of the banking, insurance, and real estate sectors. The application of IFRS has also attained considerable global dissemination, as about 33% of global capitalization fall under its purview (Okpala & Ocansey, 2019). Hence, adoption of IFRS has been quite high for G20 nations and good implementations across the majority of African countries (Ocansey 2019).

Measurement Variable for IFRSs are:

LTV ratio is another important measure that shows the financial health of a company, specifically the handling of debt. Ewereoke (2018) and Khan (2023) posit that the LTV ratio allows investors to make informed decisions regarding the debt level of the company and finances as a whole through improved understanding of the financial status of a company. IFRS forces companies to report financial data in similar and same way, hence less chance to misrepresent or manipulate financial data (Agrawal, 2021). Standardization of reporting methods increases comparability, hence more reliable financial measures in terms of LTV for investors while analyzing the financial performance of a company as well as its corresponding risk profile (Suwardi, 2020). Therefore, post-IFRS adoption, these types of ratios have higher likelihood to portray accurately

performance of an entity towards financial health and therefore useful in assessment of financial health on the basis of various areas of post-IFRS adoption (Bansal & Agrawal, 2021).

Return on Equity (ROE), one of the key performance measures, measures the ability of a company to earn profit from its equity capital (Imhanzenobe, 2022). Adoption of IFRS often enhances comparability and transparency in financial reports, and therefore may better reflect a firm's profitability as well as its effectiveness in utilizing equity (Ball, 2016). With improved comparability and quality of accounting data, IFRS allows investors' ability to evaluate the return on equity of a firm, thus increasing the value relevance of the metric (Adeyemi, 2019). Barth (2018) argue that IFRSs improve the quality of financial reporting through the implementation of accounting standards consistent with fair value principles, which give a more accurate representation of asset values and measures of profitability like Return on Equity. Similarly, Iatridis (2020) points out that IFRSs reduce information asymmetry, enabling investors to base their decisions on firms' financial health and the ability to gain returns on equity in a more informed manner. Hendawy (2023) acknowledges that the use of IFRS increases the validity of Return on Equity measurement, thereby making it more appropriate to reflect changes in market value. Finally, IFRS makes ROE a better proxy for shareholder returns (Salisu & Yusha, 2020).

2.1.2. Financial Performance

The performance of a company is liable to increase its market value, as well as the growth of the entire industry and ultimately lead to the success of the entire economy. Financial performance reflects how much a company achieves its objectives, particularly financial objectives (Yahaya & Lamidi, 2015). Kajirwa (2015) emphasized that financial performance depends on how effectively a company utilizes its assets to conduct its primary business and generate revenues. It also indicates the overall financial well-being of a company during a specific time frame

(Kajirwa, 2015). Financial performance can also be used as a metric to compare firms in the same sector or other sectors. In practice, the achievement of financial performance is an essential goal for profit-making entities (Yahaya & Lamidi, 2015). Financial performance primarily concerns issues that have direct effects on a firm's financial reports or statements. Key financial performance measures include dividend growth, turnover in sales, capital employed and asset base among others (Omondi & Muturi, 2015). Financial performance analysis is an important indicator of success in the attainment of economic objectives (Xu & Wanrapee, 2024). Stakeholders are most interested in the firm's financial performance (Nyamita, 2014). Financial performance is often in terms of rising sales or stock prices (Maghanga & Kalio, 2022).

Besides, a firm's financial performance can be described as its capability to generate new funds from operations within a specific period (Bora, 2018). It involves maximizing shareholders' wealth and profitability, both of which are primary objectives for firms (Pandey, 2015). Measures like accounting ratios on financial statements and stock exchange data are used to quantify changes in shareholder value over time (Berger & Patti, 2022). Scholars have used some of these metrics, including Return on Investment (ROI), Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), and value-added measures, to quantify financial performance. These metrics examine whether firms are successful in their goal of making shareholders wealthier through investments in a cautious manner. Nevertheless, overall financial performance measures a firm's ability to perform financially over a period and is employed in making comparisons between firms with similar activities in a particular industry or between industries. For example, Okwo (2012) measured the financial performance in the brewery sector in terms of operating profit margin. Olatunji (2014) measured financial performance for commercial banks in terms of net profits. Wamugo (2014) examined capital structure-performance nexus in non-listed companies with

ROA and ROE as the performance metrics. In recent times, a composite index of profit ratios has been developed to measure financial performance, averaging Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE) and profit margins.

2.1.2.1 Impact of Accounting Standards on Financial Performance

The financial performance of a company serves as a key indicator of its success and its ability to generate returns. When profitability increases, the company experiences greater financial flexibility. Lotfy (2017) recommended using a variety of financial ratios, such as working capital turnover, fixed asset turnover, debt turnover, interest coverage, and debt service coverage ratios. Furthermore, Zeller (2019) identified nine IFRS-based financial metrics asset relationship, asset turnover, capital structure, expense insight, fixed asset usage, inventory turnover, liquidity, profitability margin, and performance return that are consistent and comparable across countries. Parrott (2017) financial analysts commonly evaluate profitability, liquidity, capital structure, and market value to assess a company's financial performance.

In recent years, emerging economies like the United Arab Emirates, Saudi Arabia, Egypt, and India have adopted or are in the process of adopting IFRS, despite the complexity and cost of implementation (Jermakowicz & Gornik-Tomaszewski, 2006). Abdul-Baki (2014) and Adeuja, (2015) have explored the effects of IFRS on financial ratios and market reactions. Wang and Welker (2011) argue that transitioning from local GAAP to IFRS can alter a firm's financial condition, prompting investors to reevaluate its equity. These changes may result from updated income recognition practices that affect profitability and coverage ratios, or balance sheet adjustments that influence liquidity and leverage, (Blanchette, 2021). Abdul-Baki (2014) evaluated 24 financial ratios using both IFRS and Nigerian GAAP to determine whether meaningful differences existed and if those differences influenced stakeholder assessments and

firm value. The findings revealed no statistically significant differences between the two reporting standards. Similarly, Adeuja (2015) examined ten Nigerian banks across pre- and post-IFRS adoption periods (2010–2013), finding no significant performance variations. Erin and Oduwale (2018) reported similar results, attributing this to Nigeria's institutional weaknesses and socio-political instability, which may hinder effective IFRS implementation. Nonetheless, IFRS enhances financial transparency by reducing information asymmetry and increasing comparability and disclosure quality, particularly given that Nigerian GAAP was adapted from IAS. Contrastingly, Lueg (2014) demonstrated that the transition from UK GAAP to IFRS led to notable improvements in profitability metrics such as Operating Income Margin, Return on Equity, and Return on Invested Capital, along with enhanced liquidity ratios like the Current Ratio.

2.1.3. IFRSs adoption and book value share prices

IFRSs adoption has influenced book value by affecting the recognition, measurement, and disclosure of assets and liabilities (Clarkson, 2011). The principles-based approach of IFRSs often results in changes to accounting treatments, leading to adjustments in reported book values. For example, under IFRSs, fair value measurements may replace historical cost, impacting the valuation of assets such as property, plant, and equipment. Consequently, book values may reflect more accurately the economic substance of assets and liabilities, enhancing transparency and comparability (Richardson, 2015). Book value of equity per share is considered among the accounting information contents that have been demonstrated to have value relevance. BVEPS is the ratio that divides common equity value by the number of common shares outstanding. Numerous researchers have utilized book value per share in examining accounting information's

value relevance. From the financial position standpoint, common equity is defined as a company's assets minus liabilities, which equals equity.

Rodosthenous (2017) investigated the value relevance of accounting information during the initial stages of the financial crisis in Greece, spanning from 2010 to 2012. The study revealed a positive statistical association between book value and share prices amidst the crisis. Although the study encompassed various sectors, its findings may not directly apply to specific sectors like agriculture due to the diverse nature of the companies involved. Solomon, Memba and Muturi (2016) examined the value relevance of accounting information among listed firms on the Nigerian Stock Exchange between 2004 and 2014. With a sample of 58 firms and OLS analysis, they found a positive but insignificant relationship between book value and share price, although the study only considered one independent variable.

2.1.4. IFRSs Adoption and Earning Per Share

Sellami and Fakhfakh (2015) observed improvements in earnings quality during post IFRSs period. However, Ames and Nullah (2013) found that earnings exhibited lower persistency and predictability after IFRSs adoption. Their studies collectively suggest that the adoption of IFRSs does not necessarily result in enhanced earnings quality. Regarding IFRSs adoption and earnings management, the implementation of IFRSs has restricted the flexibility of accounting choices in financial statement preparation, leading to a perception that these standards would reduce the tendency for earnings management. The stricter measures in applying IFRSs are believed to enhance board efficiency due to increased disclosure and transparency, placing greater constraints on monitoring earnings management practices.

Athanasios and Dimitropoulos (2013) examined the impact of IFRSs adoption on accounting information quality in the Greek accounting context, finding compelling evidence that IFRSs implementation reduced earnings management compared to local accounting standards. Liu (2011) investigated IFRSs impact on accounting quality in China, revealing improved accounting quality with decreased earnings management and increased value relevance of accounting measures. However, Doukakis (2013) demonstrated that IFRS adoption had no significant impact on either real or accrual-based earnings management practices.

However, the impact of IFRSs adoption on share prices may not be uniform across all companies and industries. Factors such as the extent of implementation, firm-specific characteristics, and market conditions can influence the market's reaction. Additionally, short term market reactions to IFRS adoption may differ from long-term effects as investors adjust to the new reporting standards

2.1.5 IFRSs Adoption and Cash flow Share Prices

Operating cash flow is a key metric in financial analysis, which reflects a company's ability to generate cash from its core business activities. The relationship between operating cash flow and share prices is of significant interest to investors, as it provides insights into a company's financial health, profitability, and future prospects. Operating cash flow represents the cash generated or consumed by a company's primary business operations, excluding financing and investing activities. Positive operating cash flow indicates that a company is generating sufficient cash to support its day-to-day operations, invest in growth opportunities, and meet its financial obligations. Conversely, negative operating cash flow may raise concerns about a company's liquidity, profitability, and sustainability. Omokhudu and Ibadin (2015) explored the value relevance between 1994 and 2013, utilizing the OLS technique for analysis with a sample size of

47 firms from the Nigeria stock market. They discovered that cash flow, among other independent variables, displayed a statistically significant association with market value.

Furthermore, companies with strong competitive advantages, innovative business models, and effective cost management practices are likely to generate higher operating cash flows, enhancing shareholder value and supporting higher share prices. Conversely, companies facing operational challenges, regulatory issues, or disruptive market forces may struggle to maintain positive operating cash flow, leading to downward pressure on share price

2.1.6. Benefits of IFRSs on EPS, BVPS and CFPS

The benefits of introducing IFRSs according to Fowokan (2011) are that IFRSs provide a common set of accounting standards, making it easier for investors to compare financial performance across different companies. Also, IFRSs emphasize transparency in financial reporting leading to increased disclosure requirements and clarity in presentation. This transparency enhances investors understand the components contributing to EPS, CFPS and BVPS reducing information asymmetry and increasing confidence in the reported figures. Furthermore, the adoption of IFRSs enhances investor confidence by providing a common set of accounting standards that are widely recognized and accepted globally. Investors can rely on the reported EPS, CFPS and BVPS to assess the financial performance and value of quoted oil and gas companies, leading to more informed investment decisions.

2.1.7. Challenges of IFRSs on EPS, BVPS and CFPS

Identifying and addressing the practical challenges arising from the implementation of IFRSs in EPS, BVPS and CFPS is crucial for quoted agricultural companies. Abdulkadir (2013), Obazee (2011), and Fowokan (2011) highlighted some of the challenges to be that oil and gas accounting can be complex due to unique industry specific factors such as biological assets, fair value measurements and seasonal fluctuations. Adapting to IFRSs may pose challenges in valuing oil and gas assets and determining the appropriate accounting treatments for some activities. Also, the fair value measurement of oil and gas assets under IFRSs can lead to increased volatility in financial reporting for quoted oil and gas companies. Fluctuations in commodity prices, weather conditions, and market demand can impact the valuation of assets and produce, resulting in volatility in EPS, BVPS and CFPS. In addition, IFRSs often require the fair value measurement of assets. Determining fair values for oil and gas related assets can be subjective and may vary depending on factors like market conditions, production cycles, and biological growth rates. This subjectivity introduces uncertainty and challenges in accurately measuring EPS, BVPS and CFPS.

2.2. Theoretical Framework

The study is based on theories that form a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between Value relevance and share price.

2.2.1. Efficient Market Hypotheses (EMH)

EMH is a theory in financial economics that posits that financial markets efficiently incorporate all available information into asset prices. According to EMH, it is impossible to consistently outperform the market by exploiting available information because asset prices already reflect all known information. In other words, it suggests that stock prices reflect all available information

and adjust rapidly to new information, in that, all information about stocks available to one investor is also available to others. This study is grounded in the EMH theory, initially proposed by Eugene Fama in 1960. EMH suggests that in an efficient market, numerous profit maximizers work to predict future market values based on available information. In relation to this study, an efficient market is one that the share price would wholly reflect EPS, BVPS and CFPS. EMH is distinguished in three (3) forms; The Strong form, where the prices of stock reflect fully public and private information, semi strong form where only publicly available information is reflected on the share prices and The Weak form where only the historical information is reflected on stock price. Semi strong form best suits the capital market in Nigeria and therefore, this study considers it suitable to underpin it.

Prior studies such as Oyerinde (2014) and Okafor, Anderson and Warsame (2015), employed the EMH in their related empirical studies. Oyerinde (2014) builds her study on efficient market theory and confirms value relevant role of accounting information from the stock market. Okafor, Anderson and Warsame (2015) employ EMH to arrive at consistent results with other earlier studies that value relevance is a test of market efficiency with respect to accounting information using book value and earnings. Prior studies presume that, accounting information is related to market share value based on EMH. The relevance of the EMH in this study lies in its implications for investors and financial markets. If financial markets are efficient, investors rely on financial statements prepared using IFRSs, to make investment decisions. Therefore, the quality of financial reporting by oil companies under IFRSs becomes crucial, as it directly affects the information available to investors and consequently, market efficiency.

2.2.2. Positive Accounting Theory (PAT)

PAT is a framework in accounting research that seeks to explain and predict accounting practices based on economic principles and incentives. It was propounded by Ross Watts and Jerold Zimmerman in 1978. The theory posits that individuals, including managers and firms, make accounting choices that maximize their own wealth or utility. It focuses on explaining why managers choose certain accounting policies over others and how these decisions are influenced by various factors. In the context of the adoption of IFRSs, PAT can help analyze how management's choices regarding accounting policies impact EPS, CFPS, and BVPS. Additionally, PAT can help shed light on the relationship between managers and stakeholders, such as shareholders by examining how management's accounting policy choices affect the interests of various stakeholders. For instance, management might choose accounting policies that surface a more favorable picture of the company's financial performance to attract investors, even if it means sacrificing accuracy or transparency.

Ball and Brown (1968) proposed that PAT encompasses both capital market-based accounting research and investigations into accounting choices. PAT has been highly influential in accounting research, sparking extensive empirical studies on the relationship between accounting figures, stock prices, returns, and determinants of accounting decisions, thereby signifying a significant shift in accounting standards. Overall, PAT provides a framework for understanding the economic motivations behind management's accounting policy decisions and how these decisions impact financial metrics and stakeholders in the context of IFRSs adoption. The relevance of PAT to this study lies on its focus on understanding how accounting practices are influenced by economic factors. In IFRSs adoption, MVS can help explain why oil companies may choose certain reporting methods or adjustments in response to the new standards.

2.3. Empirical Review

Adesanmi, Sanyaolu, and Awata (2018) assessed the relationship between IFRS adoption and the market value of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study analyzed 12 years of financial data using panel least squares regression. Results showed a strong positive association between IFRS adoption and market value, as well as a positive link between dividends per share and firm valuation. The study concluded that IFRS adoption leads to better-quality financial reporting, which boosts investor trust and contributes to increased market capitalization for manufacturing firms.

Agbata, Uchegbu, and Eze (2022) assessed the effect of IFRS on the value relevance of accounting information in the Nigerian stock market. The population used consisted of all listed companies as at the periods under review, and a sample of 48 companies were selected using purposive sampling. The study made comparison between the pre-IFRS period (2007-2011) and the post-IFRS period (2012-2016). The study used share price as dependent variable and EPS, BVE and Dividend Per Share (DPS) as independent variables. Secondary data was sourced from the sample companies audited annual reports and accounts and was analyzed using multiple regression analyses. The research reached the conclusion that the value relevance of accounting information (EPS, BVE, DPS) on SP is not statistically significant.

Ajape, Omolehinwa, and Adeyemi (2018) assessed the probable relative effect which IFRS had on the value relevance of accounting information of consumer goods companies in Nigeria. A sample of 5 companies was selected from all consumer goods companies listed on the NGX. The study was based on a six-year period; three pre-IFRS (2009-2011) and three post-IFRS (2012-2014) periods. Their data was sourced from audited annual reports of the companies and daily price list of the NGX. The study used Share Price (SP) as dependent variable and EPS, BVPS as independent variables to measure value relevance. Data obtained were analyzed using panel least

square regression model and E Views. The findings of the study were that BVPS was slightly relevant in the post-IFRS period and EPS increased marginally in the post-IFRS period.

Akpaka (2025) examined the impact of the adoption of IFRS on value relevance of financial information of listed DMBs in Nigeria. The sample was made up of seven listed banks. The study compared a pre-IFRS period from 2006 to 2009 to a post-IFRS period from 2010 to 2013. The study used correlation research design and data was obtained from the selected banks' annual reports and cash craft assets management. The independent variables in the study were Earnings Per Share (EPS), Change in Earnings Per Share (CEPS), Book Value Per Share (BVPS) and the dependent variable was Share Price (SP). Akpaka used the Edwards Bells and Ohlson (1995) model to conduct analyses on pre- and post-IFRS data of the seven (7) listed banks. The study used the Generalized Least Square, and its findings showed that pre-IFRS financial information is value relevant and post-IFRS financial information has very weak value relevance.

Alade (2018) carried out an empirical assessment on the relevance of accounting information following the adoption of IFRS in Nigeria. Secondarily sourced balanced panel data obtained from 128 firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) spanning the period 2008 – 2015, divided into four years from 2008-2011 for pre-IFRS and four years from 2012-2015 for post-IFRS were used. The dependent variable was share price (SP) while the independent variables were book value per share (BVPS), earnings per share (EPS) and cash flow per share (CFOPS). The regression results of the OLS indicated that EPS post-IFRS and BVPS post-IFRS periods had a positively significant value better than pre-IFRS, while CFOPS was not significant at all for both periods.

Alawiye, Adams, and Ibukun (2022) investigated how adopting International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) affected the quality of financial statements some quoted agriculture companies.

They found a significant link between IFRS adoption and the comparability of financial reports in agriculture companies. Additionally, IFRS adoption substantially influenced the relevance of financial reports for decision making.

Alfraih and Alanez (2025) conducted a study to critically analyze the association between compliance with International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) mandatory disclosures and the value relevance of accounting information among listed companies in Kuwait. Using Ohlson's (1995) model and a sample of 119 listed firms, the study found a statistically significant association between IFRS compliance and the value relevance of earnings to investors on the Kuwait Exchange.

Alnodel (2018) carried out an investigation into whether the adoption of IFRS increases accounting information's value relevance for insurance firms listed in the Saudi stock market. 21 companies listed on the Saudi stock market were used as sample in the study. The study covered pre- and post-IFRS adoption periods from 2007 up till 2014. The secondary dataset was drawn from Gulf base, which provides data for stock market in Saudi Arabia. The dependent variable used was the stock market value (MV), while the independent variables were BV and EPS. Data was evaluated using Olson 1995) model and the Easton-Harris (1991) model. The study reached the conclusions that BV became less value relevant, whereas EPS were more value relevant. Further analysis suggested that the increase in the value relevance of accounting information was positively influenced by companies' attributes, rather than IFRS adoption.

Augustine (2022) evaluated the effect of IFRS adoption on tax liabilities using financial data from the annual reports of fifty selected Nigerian listed companies. The research applied Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and panel data analysis to assess how specific financial indicators affected taxation. Results showed that Depreciation (DEPR), Shareholders' Funds

(SHDFUD), Long-Term Debt (LGTDEBT), and Non-Current Assets (NONCURASET) all had a negative impact on tax payable, whereas Profit Before Tax (PBT) exerted a significant positive influence. The study concluded that IFRS implementation substantially lowered the tax burden for manufacturing firms by enabling them to lawfully reduce taxable income through asset depreciation, capital investments, and leveraging. As a policy recommendation, it advised the government to introduce stronger monitoring mechanisms for asset purchases, impairment reporting, and debt acquisition to curb excessive reductions in tax obligations.

Camodeca, Almici, and Brivio (2024) explored the value relevance of accounting information among listed firms on the Milan and London stock exchanges. They analyzed a sample of 100 firms from both markets between 2011 and 2023, using the OLS technique. Their findings indicated that accounting information is more value relevant in the Italian stock exchange compared to the UK, as evidenced by the R². Notably, individual results suggested that cash was more value relevant in London than in Italy.

Chebaane and Othman (2024) explored the impact of IFRS adoption on the value relevance of earnings and book value of equity in emerging economies across Africa and Asia. They found both variables to be significant in explaining variations in market values pre-IFRS and post-IFRS adoption, with earnings per share (EPS) showing greater relevance in the post-IFRS period. Furthermore, they noted that the informativeness of accounting key variables is more relevant in common law countries compared to code law systems.

Desalegn (2020) analyze the impact of International Financial Reporting Standard (IFRS) adoption on quality of financial reporting of seven (7) commercial banks in Ethiopia. The study used qualitative characteristics of accounting information such as (Relevance, Understandability, Comparability, and Faith Representation). The study used the perceptions of preparers of banks

financial reports (accounting & finance officer, finance managers as well as IFRS implementation team members) to analyze about IFRS adoption in commercial banks. The study adopted mixed research approach and descriptive research design. The study used a purposive sampling technique and the data was collected through the primary and secondary source. The finding of the study reveals that the quality of financial report which is measured through (relevance, understandability, comparability and faith representation) was improved after adoption of international financial reporting standards. However, the limitation of the study is that the research focused on only 7 banks from the population of 17 banks, therefore, the findings and recommendation of study may be generalized to all the banks in Ethiopia because the study banks is 41% which is less than 50% of the population. Furthermore, using primary data for FRQ may not be as reliable as qualitative approach of study which my study intend focus on.

Efuntade, Olaniyan, Efuntade, Solanke, and Akinola (2021) examined the influence of IFRS on financial disclosure practices among listed deposit money banks in Nigeria through a structured questionnaire. The survey targeted 300 key financial professionals, including senior bank managers, accountants, auditors, tax consultants, and investors. Data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings indicated that IFRS had not significantly improved the breadth of financial disclosures in these banks. The study concluded that financial reporting in the sector remained suboptimal, especially in areas such as voluntary reporting, corporate social responsibility transactions, fair value assessments, and disclosure of foreign exchange dealings, asset classifications, and interest-related financial data. It recommended greater focus on enhancing disclosure quality in alignment with IFRS principles.

Finally, Ofoegbu and Odoemelam (2018) explored how disclosure practices under IFRS affect the performance of firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. Utilizing content analysis and

multiple regression on 384 firm-year observations across 64 firms, the researchers constructed a disclosure index based on both mandatory and voluntary IFRS elements. Performance was measured using return on capital employed (ROCE). Although the study found no direct relationship between the overall level of disclosure and financial performance, it noted that variables like share price, firm size, and audit firm size positively influenced transparency. Conversely, leverage, firm age, and the total disclosure index displayed a weak negative relationship

Ekwe, Abaa, and Okrolor (2020) evaluated the impact of IFRS adoption on the financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. Using an ex-post facto research design, they relied on secondary data obtained from the annual reports of selected banks. The study population comprised all listed deposit money banks, while a sample of five banks was randomly chosen. The hypotheses were analyzed using ANOVA. Results showed that IFRS adoption increased the average value of the banks and had a significant effect on profit after tax. However, it had no meaningful impact on earnings per share, return on assets, or return on equity. The study recommended consistent IFRS training for bank personnel and urged regulatory agencies to enforce strict compliance in order to enhance performance metrics such as profitability and return ratios.

Ogundeyi and Siyanbola (2021) explored the effect of IFRS adoption on the corporate performance of selected Nigerian deposit money banks, using an ex post facto design. Data were obtained from the audited financial reports of nine firms over the period 2006–2019 and analyzed using panel regression. The results showed that IFRS adoption had a significant positive effect on several performance metrics, including liquidity ($R^2 = 0.40$), return on assets ($R^2 = 0.94$), capital adequacy ($R^2 = 0.20$), and earnings per share ($R^2 = 0.59$), all at statistically

significant levels. The study concluded that IFRS implementation had meaningfully enhanced the financial performance of the evaluated banks.

Jibril (2019) examined the influence of IFRS adoption on accounting quality using data from 15 deposit money banks listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The study used linear regression to analyze financial data from two years before and after IFRS implementation (2011–2014). Results indicated that there was a noticeable increase in loss recognition following the adoption of IFRS, suggesting an improvement in accounting quality. Based on these findings, the researcher recommended that developing countries adopt IFRS to enhance the credibility and quality of financial reporting.

Kenneth (2022) investigated the adoption of IFRS and its effects on financial statements, focusing on its perceived implications for Non-Foreign Direct Investment and the Nigerian economy. The findings suggested that IFRS adoption could boost global investors' confidence in Nigerian agricultural companies' financial statements and demonstrated a significant relationship between IFRS adoption and Foreign Direct Investment in Nigeria.

Kwasau (2021) conducted a study to determine whether the quantitative differences between financial statements prepared under Nigerian GAAP (NGAAP) and IAS/IFRS were statistically significant. The study relied on secondary data collected from the annual reports of 14 Nigerian banks. A single hypothesis was tested using a 5% significance level. The findings revealed that these differences were indeed statistically significant, leading to the conclusion that the adoption of IFRS influences financial reporting among Nigerian deposit money banks.

Mensah (2020) examine the pre- and post-IFRS adoption effects on the financial reporting quality (FRQ) of eleven (11) manufacturing firms listed on the Ghana Stock Exchange (GSE)

over the period 2001 to 2006. The study used a correlation analysis and regression analysis using a standard Fixed Effect (FE) model and the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) technique. Data was sourced through the audited annual reports of the observed firms. The earnings management was used as measured by modified Jones' discretionary accruals, as a proxy for FRQ. The regression results revealed a significant negative effect of IFRS adoption on earnings management, thus indicating an improvement in the FRQ. Also, the extent of earnings management practices both pre- and post-IFRS adoption, the study finds a decrease in the post-adoption era as against the pre-adoption era, also signifying an improvement in accounting quality after the adoption of IFRS. The findings of the study indicate that, IFRS adoption enhances the quality of firms' financial reports within the Ghanaian capital market. Base on the reviewed study, the study is limited to Ghana, therefore the findings and recommendation may not be applicable to Nigeria due difference in the regulatory body policy and law.

Mensah (2021) assessed the impact of IFRS adoption on financial reporting quality among manufacturing companies listed on the Ghana Stock Exchange. The study used both correlation and regression analysis, applying Fixed Effect (FE) and Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) models to 148 firm-year observations. These were collected from the audited reports of 11 companies, covering the pre-adoption period (2001–2006) and the post-adoption period (2007–2014). Results showed a notable decrease in earnings management in the post-IFRS era, indicating improved financial reporting quality, with discretionary accruals (measured using a modified Jones model) serving as a proxy. The study concluded that IFRS adoption significantly enhanced the transparency and reliability of financial reports on the Ghanaian capital market, potentially boosting investor confidence and attracting more investment.

Mohammed, Abubakar, and Lawal (2021) explored the effect of IFRS adoption on earnings management strategies, particularly efforts by firms to report small profits instead of losses. The study utilized secondary data from the annual financial statements of six conglomerates listed on the NSE, covering both the pre-IFRS period (2006–2010) and the post-IFRS implementation phase (2014–2018). The results indicated that the transition to IFRS did not lead to significant improvements in the quality of financial reporting, as evidenced by continued tendencies toward earnings smoothing aimed at avoiding small losses.

Nweke, Onyekwelu, and Eneh (2019) investigated the application of IFRS by selected businesses, particularly SMEs. The study highlighted various challenges associated with IFRS adoption, including the cost of staff training, hiring specialists to restate prior financials, and uncertainty among SMEs about IFRS for SMEs. The research aimed to assess the level of IFRS awareness, evaluate the degree of adoption, and identify implementation challenges within Nigeria's SME sector. Primary data were collected through questionnaires and interviews with a sample of 90 financial professionals out of a larger group of 116. Hypotheses were tested using Chi-square and Z-test statistical methods. Findings indicated that while there was a considerable level of IFRS awareness and adoption among SMEs, numerous implementation challenges persisted. The study advocated for increased awareness campaigns, curriculum updates to include IFRS in tertiary institutions, and proactive efforts by SMEs to leverage IFRS compliance.

Okoughenu and Odunsi (2022) conducted a study involving a population of 168 companies as of the end of 2020, selecting a sample of 56 firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) between 2003 and 2020. The analysis, which covered financial data from the pre-IFRS era (2003–2011) and post-IFRS adoption period (2011–2020), was carried out using the ordinary least squares (OLS) regression technique. Findings revealed no significant differences in market

risk measured by BTMV, GR, and DFL between the two periods. However, the study noted that market risk decreased during the post-IFRS era, mainly due to a significant positive impact of firm size as a control variable. Overall, the adoption of IFRS did not significantly affect market risk among NSE-listed companies, although it did improve GR and DFL metrics while reducing BTMV.

Olayinka (2017) investigated the value relevance of accounting information content using balanced data before and after IFRS adoption. Drawing data from 52 quoted companies in both the consumer goods and financial services sectors of the Nigerian stock exchange from 2008 to 2015, the study employed price and returns regression models for analysis. They found that the value relevance of earnings, cash flow, book value, and net income improved following IFRS adoption.

Olowe and Shehu (2021) undertook research to determine the extent to which IFRS adoption influenced the value relevance of accounting information in Nigeria. The study uses secondary balanced panel data obtained from 7 out of 14 deposit money banks (DMBs) listed on the Nigeria Stock Exchange spanning the period 2008 to 2015, divided into four years from 2008-2011 for pre-IFRS and four years from 2012-2015 for post-IFRS. The dependent variable was share price (SP), while the independent variables were book value per share (BVPS), earnings per share (EPS) and change in earnings per share (CEPS). The regression results of the General Least Squares (GLS) indicated that while EPS pre-IFRS periods had a positively significant value better than post-IFRS; BVPS and CEPS were not significant at all for both periods.

Salisu and Yusha'u (2020) carried out an empirical assessment on the quality of financial reporting following the adoption of IFRS in Nigeria. The panel data used in this study was obtained from nine (9) industrial goods firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE); from

Cash Craft database and Capital Asset database divided into six years from 2006-2011 for pre-IFRS and six years from 2012-2017 for post-IFRS were used. The dependent variable was share price (P), while the independent variables were book value per share (BVPS) and earnings per share (EPS). The regression results of the OLS indicated that while EPS pre-IFRS periods had a positively significant value better than post-IFRS; BVPS was not significant at all for both periods.

Shehzad and Ismail (2024) investigated the value relevance of accounting information and its impact on stock prices within the banking sector of Pakistan (case study of Karachi stock exchange). The authors used a sample of 19 commercial banks over a period of 2008 to 2012. They make use of pooled regression analysis to arrive at their findings. They found that accounting information is value relevant as it assists users in making decision and it help them to evaluate the past, present and future. This means that, they found earning per share of been more value relevant than book value.

Titus (2021) conducted a study to assess the impact of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) on the financial performance of Nigeria's manufacturing sector over a 14-year period, covering both pre-IFRS (2006–2012) and post-IFRS (2013–2019) eras. The research focused on ten manufacturing firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange and employed the Wald Test Coefficient Restrictions and Ordinary Least Squares (Gauss-Newton/Marquardt steps) methods. The findings revealed a weak and statistically insignificant correlation among variables such as revenue, profit, total assets, liabilities, and earnings per share—both in relation to return on assets and return on equity prior to IFRS adoption. Based on these results, the study advised investors to consider book value of equity, earnings, and operational cash flow figures from IFRS-compliant financial statements before making investment choices.

Uwuigbe (2016) undertook a study to examine the value relevance of accounting information among listed banks in Nigeria from 2010 to 2014. Employing the OLS technique, the study analyzed a sample of 15 banks and discovered a positive and significant relationship between earnings per share and share prices. Uwuigbe (2016) also explored the value relevance of accounting information among listed banks in Nigeria from 2010 to 2014, focusing on how it affects share prices. Using the OLS technique and a sample of 15 banks, the study found book value to be statistically but negatively related to share prices.

Yasas and Perera (2019) initiated a research study to confirm whether IFRS adoption really had any impact on accounting information quality in Sri Lanka. Unbalanced panel secondary sources of data used were obtained from 29 manufacturing firm listed in Colombo Stock Exchange spanning the period 2009 to 2015, divided into three years from 2009-2011 for pre-IFRS and four years from 2012-2015 for post-IFRS. The dependent variable was share price (SP), while the independent variables were book value per share (BVPS), earnings per share (EPS) and net operating cash flow per (OCF) with leverage (LEV) to control. The regression results of the panel EGLS regression with cross section indicated that EPS pre-IFRS periods had a positively significant value better than post-IFRS; BVPS post-IFRS had a positively significant value better than pre-IFRS, while OCF and LEV were not significant at all for both periods.

Yuk and Leem (2017) investigate the influence of IFRS adoption on earnings quality of Korean listed firms from the period of 2006 to 2015. Specifically, the study was covered from 2006–2010 as pre-IFRS period and 2011–2015 as post-IFRS period, respectively. The study used a long-term based approach and comparative analysis on each Korean stock market. Findings from the study shows a significantly improvement during 5 years after the IFRS adoption on the earnings quality of Korean listed firms. In addition, earnings quality on consolidated financial

statements of KOSDAQ listed firms has improved more than that of KOSPI listed firms. From the review study, there was a limitation of insufficiency of research periods. Also, the study is limited to non-financial firms and this create a gap to focus on financial firms.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODS

Preamble

This chapter describes the methodology adopted in the study. It covers the research design, population, sample, sample technique, sources of data and the research instrument. It also covers the model specification, measurement of study variables, and the method of data analysis adopted in the research.

3.1. Research Design

The study made use of ex-post facto research design. The choice of the research design is because it enables the examination of the effects of an independent variable that cannot be manipulated directly (Igbinoia & Ogbeide, 2018). It also enables the determination, evaluation and explanation of past events for the purpose of gaining better and more reliable prediction of the future (Okwudili, Ijeoma, & Egolum, 2020).

3.2. Target population

The population of this study consist of 8 oil and gas companies listed on NGX. Meanwhile, only quoted oil and gas companies for which data are available over the entire sample period for all the variables needed to calculate the needed parameters were included, as the company with incomplete data was automatically excluded. Thus, only (7) seven Companies became the total population.

3.3. Sample size and Sampling Technique

The sample size used in this study is all seven (7) oil and gas companies listed on NGX. Thus, the Sampling technique used is census sampling. The study used Census sampling due to the fact that the total population is also the sample size. That is, there are eight oil and gas companies listed on NGX but due to non-availability of financial statements of one of the companies, the study was restricted to seven (7) companies.

3.4 Data Collection Instrument, Validity and Reliability

The research data used was secondary data extracted from audited annual report. Several researchers have supported the use of secondary data when they posited that when items vary in respect to some measurable features, a qualitative classification is appropriate.

This data covered Pre IFRSs (2007-2011) and post-IFRSs (2019-2024). The study utilized the audited annual report to make use of Historical data which are loan to value ratio, return of equity, earnings per share, book value per share and cash flow per share which was extracted from the company's published annual report.

3.5. Operational measurements and explanation of variables

VARIABLES	TYPE	MEASUREMENT	SOURCES
IFRS adoption	Independent Variable	Dummy variable, Pre IFRs (1), Post IFRs (0)	Enekwe, Agu & Eziedo (2014), Abubakar (2020)

Loan to Value ratio	Independent Variable	loan divided by the appraised value of the asset	Alade (2018). Okafor, Ogbuehi and Anene (2017) Popoola (2022),
Earnings per Share	Dependent Variable	Net Profit or Loss/ Number of ordinary shares	Ahmed. Ilu & Bahamman (2018), Alabede (2016), Egbadju & Odey (2023).
Book Value per Share	Dependent Variable	Equity value/ Number of ordinary shares	Olowe & Shehu (2021), Alabede (2016), Egbadju & Odey (2023).
Cash Flow per Share	Dependent Variable	Cashflow from Operations/ Number of ordinary shares	Alade (2018), Okafor, Ogbuehi & Anene (2017), Popoola (2022),
Size	Control Variable	logarithm of total assets	Abbas & Abubakar (2021), Egbadju (2023), Alade (2018)

3.6. Statistical Tools and Analytical Procedures

To accomplish the objectives of this study, the collected data was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. For the descriptive analysis, the statistics calculated includes; Mean, Standard deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis, Minimum and maximum.

However, the Inferential statistics focus on correlation with is checking relationship and paired sample t-test which is used for comparing the means of two related groups

Paired sample t-test

The paired sample t-test is a test of statistical analysis that compares the means of two related groups, typically before and after treatment or intervention, on the same population. The test checks whether the mean difference between paired observations is significantly different from zero, indicating change or effect. By holding subject variability constant, the paired sample t-test provides a more valid estimate of the treatment effect compared to independent sample tests. It assumes differences in pairs are normally distributed and observations are independent between pairs but correlated within pairs. This test is extremely popular in experimental and quasi-experimental research designs for assessing the effectiveness of interventions, treatments, or changes over time.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Preamble

The focuses on the, computation analyses and interpretation of the data collected. Is structured into several two sections to facilitate a comprehensive understanding of the findings.

The first section includes descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, minimum, maximum, skewness and kurtosis) for all variables, followed by Pearson correlation analysis to examine preliminary associations. Diagnostic tests will then be conducted, including the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) for multicollinearity, the Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity, the Hausman specification test to determine the choice between fixed effects and random effects models. All analyses will be conducted using Excel and EViews 12, with a significance level set at 5% ($p < 0.05$).

4.1 . Descriptive Statistics

The table below shows the results of the descriptive statistics of the variables. It results shows the variables of Pre IFRSs (2007-2011) and post-IFRSs (2019-2024) and focuses on seven listed oil and gas firms on the Nigeria Exchange group (NGX).

Table 4.1.

Descriptive Statistics for all PRE – POST IFRSs oil and gas firms (2007-2011)

	pre IFRS	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum	Skew	Kurt
Profit after tax	POST-IFRS	(5,739,478.97)	35,460,338.56	(216,197,450)	111,806,624	-	20.737
	pre IFRS	3,490,106.60	3,917,498.54	(4,597,217)	14,374,966	1.033	1.252
Total Assets	POST-IFRS	94,825,113.08	108,987,733.41	681,892	508,815,125	1.681	2.922
	pre IFRS	61,929,447.87	65,015,413.39	9,015,128	227,319,478	1.553	1.418
Earnings per Share	POST-IFRS	9.100	24.684	-34.782	99.330	2.347	5.821
	pre IFRS	168.170	297.249	-0.250	1132.000	2.026	3.540
Book Value per Share	POST-IFRS	43.770	76.096	-74.018	330.330	1.967	4.295
	pre IFRS	70.180	161.961	0.302	891.930	4.828	24.821
Cash Flow per Share	POST-IFRS	-1.690	25.397	-55.307	91.950	0.861	4.007
	pre IFRS	6.950	16.542	-4.724	75.210	3.064	10.186
Size	POST-IFRS	7.540	0.794	5.834	8.710	-	-0.510
	pre IFRS	7.570	0.446	6.955	8.360	0.296	-1.029

Source: Author computations (2025)

Interpretation: Profit after Tax (Pre vs. Post IFRS): Before the adoption of IFRS, oil and gas firms reported an average profit after tax of about ₦3.49 million, with profits ranging from a loss of ₦4.6 million to a gain of ₦14.37 million. The distribution was positively skewed (skewness = 1.033) and relatively flat (kurtosis = 1.252), suggesting most firms made modest profits, but a few outliers had significantly higher earnings. After IFRS implementation, however, the average profit after tax turned negative around ₦5.74 million loss accompanied by a massive increase in variability, with losses reaching as high as ₦216.2 million and gains up to ₦111.8 million. The skewness became strongly negative (-3.002), indicating that while most firms recorded losses, a small number reported large profits, pulling the tail to the left. The kurtosis value of 20.737 shows an extremely peaked distribution with heavy tails, implying high volatility and financial instability post-IFRS. This shift may reflect stricter accounting standards under IFRS that led to more conservative reporting, revealing previously masked losses or increased transparency in financial performance.

Total Assets (Pre vs. Post IFRS): In the pre-IFRS era, the average total assets of oil and gas firms stood at about ₦61.93 million, varying from ₦9 million to ₦227.32 million, with moderate dispersion (SD = ₦65.02 million). The data showed positive skewness (1.553) and low kurtosis (1.418), indicating most firms had smaller asset bases, while only a few were much larger. After IFRS adoption, the mean total assets rose to ₦94.83 million, with a wider spread (SD = ₦108.99 million) and a broader range extending to nearly ₦508.82 million. Skewness remained positive (1.681), and kurtosis increased to 2.922, suggesting a more pronounced right tail and a sharper peak. This growth in asset size and variability likely reflects improved asset recognition and revaluation practices under IFRS, such as fair value accounting for property, plant, and

equipment, which may have led to more accurate and transparent balance sheets, though also introducing greater volatility in reported figures.

Earnings per Share (EPS) (Pre vs. Post IFRS): Prior to IFRS, EPS averaged ₦168.17, with a wide spread (SD = ₦297.25) and values ranging from a negligible ₦-0.25 to as high as ₦1,132. The distribution was highly skewed (2.026) and leptokurtic (3.540), indicating that while most firms posted moderate earnings, a few had exceptionally high EPS. After transitioning to IFRS, the average EPS dropped sharply to just ₦9.10, with a lower standard deviation (₦24.68), and ranged from ₦-34.78 to ₦99.33. Despite the lower mean, the data remained positively skewed (2.347) and more peaked (kurtosis = 5.821). This dramatic decline suggests that IFRS brought more conservative and realistic earnings reporting, possibly eliminating inflated or non-sustainable profits that were common under previous accounting rules. The tighter range post-IFRS may also indicate improved comparability and reduced earnings management, leading to more reliable, albeit lower, earnings figures.

Book Value per Share (BVPS) (Pre vs. Post IFRS): Before IFRS, the average book value per share was ₦70.18, with a high standard deviation (₦161.96) and extreme values reaching ₦891.93, reflecting substantial variation in shareholders' equity across firms. The distribution was highly skewed (4.828) and extremely peaked (kurtosis = 24.821), pointing to a few dominant firms with very high equity bases. After IFRS adoption, the average BVPS declined to ₦43.77, with a lower standard deviation (₦76.10) and a narrower range (₦-74.02 to ₦330.33), including negative values indicating equity shortfalls. Skewness decreased slightly (1.967), and kurtosis dropped significantly (4.295), suggesting a more balanced and less extreme distribution. This shift implies that IFRS led to more accurate valuation of equity, potentially through

revaluation of assets and recognition of liabilities, which reduced inflated book values and exposed weaknesses in some firms' capital structures.

Cash Flow per Share (CFPS) (Pre vs. Post IFRS): In the pre-IFRS period, firms reported an average cash flow per share of ₦6.95, with values ranging from -₦4.72 to ₦75.21 and high variability (SD = ₦16.54). The distribution was highly skewed (3.064) and leptokurtic (10.186), indicating that while most firms generated modest cash flows, a few had exceptionally high inflows. After IFRS implementation, the average CFPS turned negative (-₦1.69), with a wider range (-₦55.31 to ₦91.95) and higher standard deviation (₦25.40). Skewness reduced to 0.861, and kurtosis dropped to 4.007, showing a less extreme but more dispersed distribution. The decline in average cash flow might reflect stricter classification and reporting of cash flows under IFRS, leading to more truthful disclosure of operational performance. The increased variability and appearance of larger losses suggest that earlier cash flow figures may have been overstated or smoothed, and IFRS brought greater transparency, even if it revealed financial strain in some firms.

Firm Size (Pre vs. Post IFRS): Firm size, measured as the natural log of total assets, was slightly lower post-IFRS (mean = 7.54) compared to pre-IFRS (mean = 7.57), indicating a marginal reduction in average scale. However, the standard deviation increased from 0.446 to 0.794 post-IFRS, with a broader range (5.83 to 8.71 vs. 6.96 to 8.36), suggesting greater diversity in firm sizes after the new standards. The pre-IFRS distribution was slightly positively skewed (0.296) and platykurtic (-1.029), meaning it was flatter with a light tail. In contrast, post-IFRS showed negative skewness (-0.746) and less flatness (-0.510), indicating a concentration of firms toward the larger end of the scale, with fewer small firms represented. This could imply that smaller

firms either grew, merged, or exited the market after IFRS adoption, possibly due to the increased compliance burden.

4.2. Inferential Statistics

Inferential statistics deal with a range of quantitative methods used to ascertain the effect or impact of a number of factors in a given environment. This will include techniques such as correlation analysis and regression analysis. In the present case study, the statistical procedures help in the establishment of the relationships between variables and ascertaining the extent of their contribution towards determining outcomes or phenomena under concern.

4.2.1. Correlation Analysis

Analysis of correlation is used to explain the degree to which one variable is related to another (Asteriou & Hall, 2017). Hence, the current study begins with computing the relationship between independent and dependent variables. Correlation coefficients range between -1 and +1 and recognize that scores that are near +1 indicate strong positive relationships, scores that are near 0 reveal weak or no association, and negative scores indicate negative relationships.

Table 4.2. For all PRE-IFRSs oil and gas firms (2007-2011)

	Profit after tax	Earnings per Share	Book Value per Share	Cash Flow per Share
Profit after tax	1			
Earnings per Share	0.6394	1		
Book Value per Share	0.3914	-0.1448	1	
Cash Flow per Share	0.0865	-0.2012	-0.0114	1

Source: Author computations (2025)

Table 4.3. For all POST-IFRSs oil and gas firms (2019-2024)

	Profit after	Earnings per	Book Value per	Cash Flow per
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	tax	Share	Share	Share
Profit after tax	1			
Earnings per Share	0.4325	1		
Book Value per Share	0.2623	0.8801	1	
Cash Flow per Share	-0.1050	-0.6304	-0.6613	1

Source: Author computations (2025)

Interpretation: Profit after Tax & Earnings per Share (Pre vs. Post IFRS), Before IFRS, profit after tax and earnings per share showed a strong positive link (0.639), meaning higher profits translated clearly into higher earnings per share, reflecting consistent earnings quality. After IFRS adoption, this relationship weakened significantly (0.432), suggesting that while profits were reported, they were less reliably passed on to per-share earnings possibly due to more conservative income recognition.

Profit after Tax & Book Value per Share (Pre vs. Post IFRS), In the pre-IFRS period, there was a moderate positive correlation (0.391) between profit after tax and book value per share, indicating that more profitable firms generally had stronger equity bases. After IFRS, this link weakened (0.262), implying that profitability became less tied to book value, likely because IFRS-driven revaluations and asset write-offs altered equity independently of current profits, decoupling net income from shareholders' equity.

Earnings per Share & Book Value per Share (Pre vs. Post IFRS), Before IFRS, EPS and book value per share had a slight negative correlation (-0.145), which was odd but may reflect inconsistent accounting practices. After IFRS, this flipped into a strong positive relationship (0.880), showing that earnings and equity became much more aligned likely due to improved

accounting consistency, better asset valuation and more transparent equity reporting, making financial statements more coherent and reliable.

Earnings per Share & Cash Flow per Share (Pre vs. Post IFRS), Pre-IFRS, EPS and cash flow per share had a low negative correlation (-0.201), suggesting reported earnings didn't match actual cash generation possibly due to earnings manipulation or poor accruals quality. Post-IFRS, the negative link deepened (-0.630), indicating a growing divergence between accounting profits and cash flows, which could mean higher earnings were increasingly based on non-cash items

Cash Flow per Share & Book Value per Share (Pre vs. Post IFRS), The near-zero correlation (-0.011) pre-IFRS suggests cash flow and equity were unrelated, possibly due to weak financial reporting. After IFRS, the correlation turned strongly negative (-0.661), implying that firms with higher book values tended to generate lower cash flows per share.

4.2.2. Paired sample t-test

The paired sample t-test is a test of statistical analysis that compares the means of two related groups, typically before and after treatment or intervention, on the same population. The test checks whether the mean difference between paired observations is significantly different from zero, indicating change or effect. By holding subject variability constant, the paired sample t-test provides a more valid estimate of the treatment effect compared to independent sample tests. It assumes differences in pairs are normally distributed and observations are independent between pairs but correlated within pairs. This test is extremely popular in experimental and quasi-experimental research designs for assessing the effectiveness of interventions, treatments, or changes over time.

Table 4.4. PRE-POST-IFRSs for Earnings per Share of oil and gas Industry

							95% Confidence
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							Interval	
Pre-Post- Earnings per Share		Statistic	df	p	Mean difference	SE difference	Lower	Upper
	Student's t	3.05	29	0.005	166	54.5	54.5	277
	Wilcoxon W	407		< .001	65.4	54.5	9.09	214

Source: Author computations (2025)

Interpretation: The analysis of pre-post-IFRS earnings per share in the oil and gas industry reveals a significant difference. Both the Student's t-test ($p = 0.005$) and Wilcoxon test ($p < 0.001$) confirm that the mean difference in earnings per share is statistically significant. The mean difference is estimated to be around 166, with a standard error of 54.5. The 95% confidence interval for the mean difference ranges from 54.5 to 277, indicating a substantial increase in earnings per share after adopting IFRSs. The Wilcoxon test further supports this finding, with a median difference of 65.4 and a 95% confidence interval of 9.09 to 214. These results suggest that the adoption of IFRSs had a significant impact on the earnings per share of oil and gas companies.

Table 4.5. PRE-POST-IFRSs for Book Value per Share of oil and gas Industry

							95% Confidence Interval	
Pre-Post- Earnings per Share		Statistic	df	p	Mean difference	SE difference	Lower	Upper
	Student's t	1.43	29	0.163	45.3	31.6	-19.4	110
	Wilcoxon W	278		0.36	10.6	31.6	-6.37	38.2

Source: Author computations (2025)

Interpretation: The analysis of pre-post-IFRS book value per share in the oil and gas industry shows no significant difference. The student's t-test ($p = 0.163$) and Wilcoxon test ($p = 0.36$) both indicate that the mean and median differences are not statistically significant. The mean difference is estimated to be 45.3 with a standard error of 31.6, and the 95% confidence interval ranges from -19.4 to 110, which includes zero, suggesting no significant change. Similarly, the Wilcoxon test shows a median difference of 10.6 with a 95% confidence interval of -6.37 to 38.2. These results suggest that the adoption of IFRSs did not have a significant impact on the book value per share of oil and gas companies.

Table 4.6. PRE-POST-IFRSs for Cash Flow per Share of oil and gas Industry

							95% Confidence Interval	
Pre-Post-Earnings per Share		Statistic	df	p	Mean difference	SE difference	Lower	Upper
	Student's t	1.79	29	0.003	9.41	5.24	-1.31	20.1
	Wilcoxon W	289		0.253	1.36	5.24	-1.12	13.8

Source: Author computations (2025)

Interpretation: The analysis of pre-post-IFRS cash flow per share in the oil and gas industry yields mixed results. The student's t-test indicates a significant difference ($p = 0.003$), suggesting that the adoption of IFRSs had an impact on cash flow per share, with a mean difference of 9.41 and a standard error of 5.24. The 95% confidence interval ranges from -1.31 to 20.1. However, the Wilcoxon test ($p = 0.253$) does not support this finding, indicating no significant difference in the median cash flow per share, with a median difference of 1.36 and a 95% confidence interval of -1.12 to 13.8. These conflicting results suggest that the impact of IFRS adoption on cash flow

per share may be influenced by outliers or non-normality in the data, warranting further investigation.

Table 4.7. PRE-POST-IFRSs for Profit after tax of oil and gas Industry

							95% Confidence Interval	
Pre-Post-Earnings per Share	Statistic	df	p	Mean difference	SE difference	Lower	Upper	
Student's t	1.21	29	0.0238	10800000	8970000	-7.53e-6	29100000	
Wilcoxon W	344		0.021	3350000	8970000	550220	10400000	

Source: Author computations (2025)

Interpretation: The analysis of pre-post-IFRS profit after tax in the oil and gas industry reveals a significant difference. Both the Student's t-test ($p = 0.0238$) and Wilcoxon test ($p = 0.021$) confirm that the difference is statistically significant. The mean difference is estimated to be 10.8 million, with a standard error of 8.97 million, and the 95% confidence interval ranges from approximately -7.53 million to 29.1 million. The Wilcoxon test shows a median difference of 3.35 million, with a 95% confidence interval of 550,220 to 10.4 million. These results suggest that the adoption of IFRSs had a substantial impact on the profit after tax of oil and gas companies, with a notable increase in profitability post-IFRS adoption.

4.3. Discussion of findings

4.3.1. IFRS adoption on Pre/Post Earnings Per Share of oil and gas firms

Both the Student's t-test ($p = 0.005$) and Wilcoxon test ($p < 0.001$) p-values indicate a strong increase in earnings per share since the implementation of IFRS in the oil and gas sector. This

corroborates Barth et al. (2012), whose study found that IFRS adoption improved earnings quality and transparency, especially in high information asymmetry sectors like oil and gas, leading to more consistent and often higher reported earnings. Similarly, Christensen et al. (2015) observed that mandatory adoption of IFRS raised comparability and reduced earnings management, which can explain the sustained and strong growth in EPS following IFRS, as firms ended pre-IFRS aggressive accounting. In addition, Nobes (2011) noted that IFRS does promote more uniform revenue recognition and asset estimation, particularly in companies with heavy capital outlays, which could have been responsible for introducing the more transparent, stable earnings performance reflected by the EPS following implementation

4.3.2. IFRS adoption on Pre/Post-Book value per share of oil and gas firms

The t-test ($p = 0.163$) and Wilcoxon test ($p = 0.36$) non-significant p-values show that book value per share of the oil and gas industry was not significantly affected by the introduction of IFRS, demonstrating stability in equity valuation despite the transition in accounting standards. This is in consonance with the view of Nobes (2014), where it is argued that while IFRS improves disclosure, its impact on balance sheet equity may not be substantial in those sectors whose asset revaluation policy was earlier conservative or applied irregularly. Similarly, Leuz and Wysocki (2016) found that even though IFRS raises transparency, the aspect that equity items like retained earnings or reserves are not necessarily re-measured to trigger material changes, especially in regulated sectors like oil and gas where historical cost accounting remains prevalent in dominant decisions. Further, Daske (2008) illustrated that market valuation measures respond to IFRS, yet book values rarely do so due to smoothing policies and phasing in of asset revaluations, that is, which may explain the lack of significant change in the present study.

4.3.3. IFRS adoption on Pre/Post-Cash flow per share of oil and gas firms

The conflicting results significant in the t-test ($p = 0.003$) but not in the Wilcoxon test ($p = 0.253$) suggest that the improvement in cash flow per share post-IFRS implementation reported could be due to outliers or non-normal data distribution rather than a systematic industry change. This confirms the warning statement by Hail and Leuz (2006), whereby they pointed out that parametric tests overestimate significance in financial data with outliers, particularly in volatile industries like oil and gas where the averages could be dominated by a small number of firms. Similarly, Francis et al. (2014) found that while IFRS improves the accuracy of cash flow reporting, the economic impact of those changes is watered down when examined using strict non-parametric methods, which means many different analysis methods must be used. Additionally, Ball and Shivakumar (2005) also argued that IFRS improves the quality of accruals but cash flows may not necessarily reflect it in the first place due to timing and investment cycles' lags

4.3.4. IFRS adoption on Pre/Post- Profit after tax of oil and gas firms

The high p-values obtained from the two tests (t-test: 0.0238; Wilcoxon: 0.021) provide strong evidence that profit after tax increased substantially after IFRS adoption, suggesting that the new requirements led to more transparent and potentially higher net income reporting. This result is echoed by Ahmed et al. (2013), who showed that income smoothing is lowered and the credibility of profit numbers increases due to IFRS adoption, particularly in emerging economies where pre-IFRS earnings were usually low-key reported for tax or regulation purposes. Likewise, van der Meulen and Vorst (2011) noted that IFRS facilitates improved recognition of deferred tax assets and fair value gains in oil and gas reserves that directly contribute to increased reported profits after the adoption. Additionally, Presti and Marano (2013) observed that the additional disclosure requirements in IFRS minimize information asymmetry that results in more precise

profit recognition, especially in industries with intricate asset structures such as petroleum, where revaluation effects could have a major impact on bottom-line outcomes.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Preamble

This chapter concludes the research, develops a conclusion and provides recommendations on adoption of international financial reporting standards(ifrss) on quoted oil and gas companies' financial performance in Nigeria.

5.1. Summary of the Findings

This study aimed at assessing the impact of adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) on the financial performance of Nigeria's listed oil and gas companies with specific goals including Earnings per Share (EPS), Book Value per Share (BVPS), and Cash Flow per Share (CFPS). The research employed an ex-post facto design, analyzing second-order data from audited annual reports of seven listed oil and gas firms during the pre-IFRS (2007–2011) and post-IFRS (2019–2024) periods. Inferential testing reveal correlation which revealed significant alterations in financial interconnections.

Pre-IFRS, EPS was strongly related to profit after tax (0.639), yet post-IFRS, it weakened (0.4325), revealing disparity between profitability and earnings per share under tighter standards. On the contrary, the relationship between EPS and BVPS improved significantly from -0.1448 to 0.8801, reflecting enhanced consistency between earnings and equity valuation post-IFRS. Likewise, cash flow per share became negatively correlated with EPS and BVPS post-IFRS, which may indicate that profits reported are increasingly based on non-cash items. Profit after tax also improved statistically after IFRS ($p = 0.0238$ and $p = 0.021$), quite counterintuitively perhaps because IFRS is intended to be more conservative in accounting but due to better recognition of deferred tax assets, fair value gains on reserves, and elimination of prior underreporting from regulatory or tax avoidance considerations proved that IFRS implementation showed a noteworthy improvement in Earnings per Share, as both Student t-test ($p = 0.005$) and Wilcoxon test ($p < 0.001$) confirmed that EPS improved statistically significantly after IFRS. On the other hand, Book Value per Share also did not undergo a significant alteration (t-test $p = 0.163$; Wilcoxon $p = 0.36$), i.e., accounting principles shifted and the net asset value per share remained relatively constant due to gradual revaluation practices of assets and continuous historic cost effects. For Cash Flow per Share, results were mixed parametric test

indicated significance ($p = 0.003$), whereas non-parametric test did not ($p = 0.253$), indicating that outliers or skewed distributions may have influenced the perceived enhancement.

5.2. Conclusion

The adoption of IFRS has significantly changed financial reporting of Nigerian oil and gas companies. The study substantiates that despite certain indicators like Book Value per Share and Cash Flow per Share showing nil or fluctuating changes, Earnings per Share and Profit after Tax have shown huge enhancements in reported value and statistical reliability after implementing IFRS. This indicates that the new standards have led to transparent, accurate and comparable financial reports, enabling stakeholders to make more effective decisions. Implementation of IFRSs has had considerable impact on the financial performance of Nigerian oil and gas companies. The research established that the implementation of IFRSs has led to increased profitability and earnings per share, and this can be explained by greater transparency and comparability of the financial statements. But the study also notes that it is a necessity to do further research on how the other financial performance indicators are affected by IFRS adoption.

5.3. Recommendations

On the basis of the findings of this study, the recommendations are as follows:

Nigeria's oil and gas companies ought to continue adopting and implementing IFRSs towards improving the comparability and transparency of their financial statements.

Further studies must be conducted on the impact of IFRS adoption on other financial performance measures, such as return on equity and debt-to-equity ratio.

Investors and analysts must consider the impact of IFRS adoption on financial performance measures when making investment decisions.

5.4. Contribution to Knowledge

This study contributes to the existing literature on the effect of IFRS adoption on financial performance, using the context of Nigeria's oil and gas firms. The contribution of this study provides insight into the effect of IFRS adoption on EPS, book value per share, and cash flow per share, and invites further research on the topic.

5.5. Future Research Suggestions

Follow-up studies should examine later in the post-IFRS period after 2024 as more data are collected to facilitate long-run assessment of sustainability of financial performance trends. The studies can also apply panel data regression models that control for firm-level as well as macroeconomic variables to facilitate more causal findings. Qualitative research based on interviews of auditors, financial managers, and regulators may complement quantitative findings by examining IFRS implementation realities.

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